

CAPABILITY, OPPORTUNITY, AND MOTIVATION LEVEL IN TABLE TENNIS THROUGH CLUB MODE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This study deeply explores the capability, opportunity and motivation level of students in table tennis teaching, aiming to provide a basis for improving the learning effect of students using the club mode teaching approach. Research questions revolve around students' physical and mental abilities, social and psychological opportunities, and intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. This study also focuses on whether there are significant differences in these aspects among students of different ages, genders and majors. Key findings revealed that table tennis athletes possessed high level of physical and psychological capabilities. Athletes demonstrated high social and psychological opportunities, and high intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. No significant difference in capabilities, opportunities, and Motivation when grouped as to age. No significant difference in opportunities and motivation in terms of sex, while there was a significant difference in the capability in terms of sex. Significant difference was revealed on capabilities, opportunities, and Motivation when grouped as to majors. Based on the research results, it is recommended to evaluate students' learning progress and develop targeted teaching strategies to improve students' mastery of table tennis and enhance their competitive level. Overall, this study will provide useful reference for table tennis club mode teaching approach and promote students' learning effect and competitive performance. For administrators to allocate resources for facilities and provide support for teacher training.

Keywords: *Capability, club mode teaching, opportunity, motivation level, table tennis*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher-Coach plays a vital role in promoting physical and mental well-being of the learners and players. They feel responsible to promote wellness and well-being of students especially in the current information age where a significant proportion of the population has adopted a sedentary lifestyle. Student actions that facilitate effective learning and constructive interaction within the community, as articulated by Wang (2020) states that behaviors are cultivated within and beyond the school environment, including activities within the Table Tennis Club. Understanding and managing student behavior is crucial for developing emotional intelligence, fostering positive relationships, and instilling vital life skills such as responsible decision-making. Students have the flexibility to select courses at any point during the week or attend classes with any teacher offering the same course (Club) at any time slot throughout the week. Enabling them to select courses that align with their abilities and interests, and stimulate their subjective initiative of active learning and seeking desires, as well as maximize students' learning outcomes (Tian, 2019). The course selection mechanism of the school leads to physical education so that every teacher will have a high sense of responsibility for his work and a sense of urgency to improve his ability; It breaks the traditional unit teaching system, makes the goal of college physical education more suitable for the development of students' personality, and combines it with the long-term goal of cultivating lifelong healthy qualified talents.

Table tennis is an example of an open skill sport, which rapidly raises levels of tension and negative thinking and is difficult to manage the emotions of the players. As a result, table tennis is one of the most difficult sports for an athlete to continually sustain top performance (Bai Ning and Magalona, 2024). Interventions in applied sport psychology are typically implemented using the psychological skills training model, which refers to the "systematic and consistent practice of mental or psychological skills for the purpose of improving performance, increasing enjoyment, or achieving greater sport and physical activity satisfaction" (Weinberg, 2019).

Student or athlete's behaviors refer to acquired actions that facilitate effective learning and constructive interaction within the community, as articulated by Wang (2020). Through club mode teaching, table tennis students basically master the position, posture, footwork, serve, forehand fast attack, backhand push (dial ball) and other technology; table tennis teachers use various forms of teaching methods, make technical action learning from easy to difficult, different, step by step, gradually improve, and pay attention to ideological and political leading role, cultivate students' lifelong sports thought. Furthermore, Bai Ning and Magalona (2024) stressed that coaches in tennis demonstrated a very high level of confidence, social skills and decision-making abilities which influence the athlete's performance.

To be able to investigate the table tennis club mode teaching using Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation, Behavior Analysis a COM-B framework (Michie, et al., 2014) was used. It is a procedure of investigation that is highly used in humanities field for behavioral analysis. This study will attempt to employ this framework in Physical

Education. It identifies three factors that need to be present for any behavior to occur: capability, opportunity, and motivation.

This study intends to analyze the behavior of the club members in Table Tennis as this may provide insights into the current ability of club mode teaching, specifically in Table Tennis. Michie et al. (2011) suggest that individuals require capability (C), opportunity (O), and motivation (M) to engage in a behavior (B). They introduced the COM-B model to facilitate the comprehension of behavior within a given context and to identify behavioral targets, forming the foundation for designing effective interventions.

Research Questions

To give light to the problem, the researchers sought to answer the capability, opportunity and motivation levels of Table Tennis athletes.

1. What is the capability level of the students in table tennis in terms of:
 - 1.1 Physical Abilities
 - 1.2 Selected Psychological Instruct
2. What is the opportunity level of the students in table tennis in terms of:
 - 2.1 Social Opportunities
 - 2.2 Psychological Opportunities
3. What is the motivation level of the students in table tennis in terms of:
 - 3.1 Intrinsic Motivation
 - 3.2 Extrinsic Motivation
4. Is there a significant difference in the capability level, opportunity level, and motivation level of the students in table tennis under the club mode teaching when grouped in terms of:
 - 4.1 Age
 - 4.2 Sex
 - 4.3 Major

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the capability level, opportunity level, and motivation level of the students in table tennis under the club mode teaching when grouped in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Major

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized quantitative research approach, focusing on collecting, processing, testing, and analyzing information to derive meaningful conclusions. The primary objective is to evaluate the capability level of student-respondents, gauge the motivation levels among students in the context of table tennis, and assess the opportunity level, defined as the perceived satisfaction derived from the environment by the students. Descriptive research is a sort of research that aims to characterize a condition, problem, or occurrence in a methodical, factual, accurate, and objective manner. It tries to put into words what is. Adams & Lawrence (2019) mentioned that descriptive research collected information about the overall distribution characteristics and provides information about the overall structure, phenomena, etc. Descriptive statistics used a strict random sampling method to select the study population for statistical processing of the information obtained. The COM-B Model developed by Susan Michie, et.al 2011, Barker, et. al. (2016) was used.

Research Locale and Participants

This study was conducted in 5 universities in Anhui province, China. A total number of 300 respondents who were enrolled in Table Tennis Physical Education classes through club Mode Teaching.

Research Instrument

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used. To ensure the quality of the instrument, the researcher-made questionnaire underwent validation by five professors who are experts in the field of Table Tennis and coaching. In crafting the instrument, careful consideration was given to the requirements for designing a strong data collection tool. These experts were provided with the instrument for critiquing, reviewing, and evaluating its content. The primary objective at this stage was to ascertain the validity of the questionnaire items. A mean score of 4.42 which was very high validity was used for pilot test involving 20 participants who are not part of the actual respondents but had been granted permission to participate in the pilot testing phase

Data Gathering Procedure

Data was collected using structured questionnaires and assessments designed to measure capability, opportunity, and motivation. The instrument assessed for validity and reliability using Cronbach Alpha. After an excellent result was obtained the necessary permission from the university president to conduct the study to the actual participants. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution was employed to characterize the research variables. The researcher, personally administering the questionnaire, took care to ensure the comfort of the participants during

the process. Data collection and processing procedures were carefully planned to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data. Subsequently, quantitative data analyses were conducted.

Data Analysis

The study follows the ethical standard of research. After gathering all the data, the researchers used the Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation, independent t test and ANOVA.

RESULTS

This part includes the discussion of results.

Table 1 *The Capability Level of The Students in Table Tennis in Terms of Physical Abilities and selected Psychological Instruct*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
Physical Abilities	2.91	0.74	High
Selected Psychological Instruct	3.14	0.64	High

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Very low; 1.76-2.50 Low; 2.51-3.25 High; 3.26-4.00 Very high

Table 2 *The Opportunity Level of The Students in Table Tennis in Terms of Social and Psychological Opportunities*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
Social Opportunities	3.14	0.64	High
Psychological Opportunities	3.22	0.62	High

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Very low; 1.76-2.50 Low; 2.51-3.25 High; 3.26-4.00 Very high

Table 3 *The Motivation Level of The Students in Table Tennis in Terms of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
Intrinsic Motivation	3.15	0.64	High
Extrinsic Motivation	2.75	0.76	High

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Very low; 1.76-2.50 Low; 2.51-3.25 High; 3.26-4.00 Very high

Table 4.1 *Significant Difference in The Capability Level of The Students in Table Tennis Under the Club Mode Teaching in Terms of Age*

Indicators	T -value	P -value	VI	Ho
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Age	1.19	.11	NS	Accepted
Sex				
Male	3.69	.00	S	Rejected
Female	3.62	.01	S	Rejected
Major	1.09	.01	S	Rejected

Table 4.2 Significant Difference in The Opportunity Level of The Students in Table Tennis Under the Club Mode Teaching in Terms of Age

Indicators	T -value	P -value	VI	Ho
Age	0.43	.33	NS	Accepted
Sex				
Male	0.65	.26	NS	Accepted
Female	0.67	.25	NS	Accepted
Major	2.19	.01	S	Rejected

Table 4.3

Significant Difference in The Motivation Level of The Students in Table Tennis Under the Club Mode Teaching

Indicators	T -value	P -value	VI	Ho
Age	0.61	.54	NS	Accepted
Sex				
Male	0.59	.57	NS	Accepted
Female	0.84	.43	NS	Accepted
Major	2.10	.03	S	Rejected

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the statistical results on the Capability Level of Students in Table Tennis in Terms of Physical Abilities which refers to the extent of their physical proficiency, encompassing strength, speed, agility, coordination, endurance, and flexibility. This level is crucial in executing table tennis techniques and movements effectively. Understanding this capability level provides a foundation for assessing students' readiness, identifying training needs, and designing targeted interventions to enhance their performance. Furthermore, the outcomes of the evaluation of students' capability levels in table tennis, specifically focusing on Physical Abilities with a mean 2.91 and an SD of .74 which is high. The findings suggest potential areas for improvement, emphasizing the importance of refining aspects related to strength and adaptability to emerging trends. Moreover, the analysis of physical capabilities in table tennis among students under club mode teaching reveals commendable strengths in various dimensions. Petersons et al. (2019), they revealed that university students are both highly active and highly sedentary. The

curriculum demonstrates efficacy in cultivating key aspects of physical capability. However, the nuanced findings highlight specific areas that warrant attention for further refinement and enhancement, emphasizing the iterative nature of educational practices in sports. The results align with previous research by Fawver et al., (2019), who emphasized the importance of a comprehensive curriculum in Table Tennis teaching, covering technical skills, tactical concepts, and age-appropriate physical exercises. Additionally, their study corroborates the need for teachers to employ modern teaching methods in tennis courses, reflecting the broader applicability of these conclusions. Manubag et al., (2023) stressed that the multifaceted nature of capability development is further unraveled as these studies collectively reveal the symbiotic relationship between training methods and skill enhancement

On the capability level of students in table tennis, as measured by Selected Psychological Instruct, the indicators presented in Table 1 provide valuable insights into various psychological factors that contribute to success in table tennis. The overall result, with a mean score of 3.14, reinforces the high psychological capability of the students in table tennis. This assessment aligns with the scale provided, categorizing the psychological capability as "High." This analysis provides a solid foundation for further investigations and the development of targeted interventions to enhance psychological aspects crucial for success in the sport. The integration of club mode teaching can be tailored to capitalize on these strengths and address specific areas for improvement in the psychological profile of table tennis players. The findings resonate with existing literature on the importance of psychological factors in sports performance (Wang et al., 2023). Psychological skills such as concentration, resilience, and motivation have been recognized as key contributors to success in sports, including table tennis. While our study indicates high capabilities in table tennis through club mode teaching, diverse perspectives from (Zhang et al., 2019) underscores the need for nuanced considerations in assessing and enhancing student skills.

Table 2 shows the opportunity level of students in table tennis, as assessed in terms of social opportunities, plays a pivotal role in shaping their overall experience and performance in the sport. The mean score of 3.14, categorizes the social opportunity level as "High." This aligns with the scale provided, highlighting the generally positive social environment within the context of table tennis clubs. Moreover, the analysis of social opportunities in table tennis emphasizes the importance of effective communication, community building, and diverse competitive experiences. While the overall social opportunity level is high, targeted improvements in competition variety may further enhance the holistic development of table tennis players within club settings. These findings provide a foundation for refining club mode teaching strategies and establishing an evaluation framework that addresses both psychological and social dimensions for comprehensive player development. Deelen et al., (2019) study's focus on effective communication and community building in table tennis aligns with supports the need for enhanced competition variety, reinforcing our findings. Additionally, endorse the broader social benefits identified, enriching the understanding of social opportunities and supporting the development of targeted club mode teaching strategies.

The opportunity Level of Students in Table Tennis in Terms of Psychological Opportunities refers to the availability of psychological resources and support that enable students to develop and maintain positive psychological states for optimal performance. This includes having access to mental training, counseling, and other psychological interventions that help them manage stress, enhance concentration, maintain motivation, and cope with setbacks. These psychological opportunities are crucial for fostering a resilient and confident mindset in table tennis players. Table 2 discloses the findings of an evaluation exploring the opportunity level of students in table tennis, specifically delving into Psychological Opportunities. The highest mean scores spotlight strengths within the psychological dimension, revealing positive aspects. Concurrently, the lowest mean scores draw attention to potential areas for improvement, providing valuable insights into the psychological opportunities influencing students engaged in table tennis through club mode teaching.

The mean score of 3.22, categorizes the psychological opportunity level as "High." This aligns with the scale provided, indicating that students in table tennis clubs have access to a rich array of psychological opportunities for development. Moreover, the analysis of psychological opportunities in table tennis through club mode teaching highlights the positive impact on students' mental skills and well-being. The consistently high scores across indicators indicate a robust psychological support system within the club setting. These findings provide a foundation for the development of targeted interventions and the formulation of an evaluation framework to enhance psychological aspects of player development in table tennis. The focus on mental skills training and positive psychological attributes in table tennis, as reflected in the indicators. The broader psychological benefits identified in Indicators 6 to 10 align with the findings of Deelen et al., (2019), emphasizing the positive impact of sports participation on resilience, self-confidence, goal-setting, and emotional regulation. The psychological dimension is essential for enhancing concentration, resilience, and intrinsic motivation, all contributing to optimal performance (Xu & Tang, 2022).

Table 3 presents the Motivation Level of Students in Table Tennis in Terms of Intrinsic Motivation refers to the internal drive and desire that students have to engage in and excel at table tennis. This motivation is fueled by their enjoyment of the sport, a sense of accomplishment, and the personal satisfaction derived from skill development and achievement. It is a critical aspect of their overall motivation and crucial for sustained engagement and progress in table tennis. It highlights the findings of an evaluation probing into the motivation levels of students in table tennis, specifically examining Intrinsic Motivation. The highest mean scores spotlight the strengths within this motivational dimension, elucidating positive aspects. Meanwhile, the lowest mean scores draw attention to potential areas for enhancement, providing a nuanced understanding of the intrinsic motivational factors influencing students engaged in table tennis through club mode teaching.

Additionally, it provides insights into the intrinsic motivation level of students in table tennis within the context of club mode teaching. Intrinsic motivation, characterized

by a genuine love for the sport and an internal drive to engage in table tennis, plays a crucial role in shaping a student's commitment and enjoyment of the game. The analysis of the indicators reveals a generally high level of intrinsic motivation among the students, as reflected by the mean scores and standard deviations. It highlights the students' enjoyment, positive affective responses, and the acknowledgment of personal development as key components of intrinsic motivation. This aligns with existing literature emphasizing the importance of enjoyment and personal growth in sustaining intrinsic motivation (Weinberg & Gould, 2023). The mean score of 3.15, categorizes the intrinsic motivation level as "High." This aligns with the scale provided, indicating that students participating in table tennis through club mode teaching are intrinsically motivated, driven by the inherent satisfaction derived from the sport. The emphasis on enjoyment, positive affective responses, and personal development in fostering intrinsic motivation in table tennis aligns with the perspectives. The findings related to deep passion, goal-setting, and sustained commitment are consistent with the principles of self-determination theory.

The motivation level of students in table tennis in terms of extrinsic motivation refers to the external factors that influence their desire to participate in and perform well in the sport. This includes rewards, recognition, praise, competition, and other external incentives that drive their motivation. Extrinsic motivation can be important in motivating students initially, but it is typically less sustainable in the long run compared to intrinsic motivation, which is rooted in personal enjoyment and satisfaction. Table 3 illuminates the outcomes of an evaluation probing into the motivation levels of students in table tennis, specifically exploring Extrinsic Motivation. The highest mean scores underscore areas of strength within this facet of motivation, shedding light on positive aspects. Chelladurai & Kim (2022) have examined the social dynamics in table tennis clubs, emphasizing the importance of a supportive community in bolstering motivation and commitment among players. Meanwhile, the lowest mean scores draw attention to potential areas for improvement, offering crucial insights into the extrinsic motivational factors influencing students engaged in table tennis through club mode teaching.

A mean score of 2.75, categorizes the extrinsic motivation level as "High." This reflects the influence of various external factors such as awards, recognition, and competition on students' motivation to participate in table tennis. Moreover, the analysis of extrinsic motivation in table tennis reveals a complex interplay of factors. While certain external rewards and recognition contribute to a high extrinsic motivation level, there is variability in responses, and some aspects of extrinsic motivation exhibit lower levels. These findings underscore the importance of understanding the nuanced relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in the context of table tennis club teaching. The observation of a mixed profile in extrinsic motivation within table tennis aligns with the findings of Akelaitis and Malinauskas (2019), who emphasize the limited effectiveness of certain external rewards in sustaining engagement. The recognition of variability in responses and lower levels in specific aspects resonates with their perspective. While the overall categorization as "High" in extrinsic motivation aligns with the multifaceted nature of external factors, acknowledging the nuanced relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, as highlighted by additional research, enriches the understanding

of the motivational dynamics in table tennis clubs. The recognition of intrinsic motivation's role in sustaining long-term commitment in sports, aligns with the findings of the current study. Additionally, Lim emphasize the significance of extrinsic motivation in providing additional incentives and rewards, support the conclusion that both intrinsic and extrinsic factors contribute to the overall high motivation level within club mode teaching. These readings reinforce the success of the teaching approach in creating a balanced motivational climate, addressing diverse student needs, and contributing to sustained engagement and performance in table tennis.

Table 4.1 shows the significant difference on the capability of students under club mode teaching in terms of sex and their majors but no significant difference in terms of age. The data signifies that club mode teaching may distinctly impact certain aspects of capability, emphasizing the need for targeted instructional strategies. The mean differences, standard errors, and confidence intervals further substantiate these findings. While some capabilities benefit significantly, others remain consistent across majors. This analysis contributes valuable insights for tailoring teaching approaches in table tennis across diverse skill domains, forming the groundwork for a specialized evaluation framework. The detailed data-driven approach underscores the multifaceted impact of club mode teaching on students' capabilities, providing a comprehensive understanding for educators and practitioners in the field.

Table 4.2 shows the significant difference in the opportunity level in table tennis under club mode teaching in terms of major. While no significant difference on age and sex when categorized as male and female. Hatzipanagos et al. (2020) as cited by Chen (2024) stressed evaluation enables teachers to provide feedback and guidance to students based on their actual performance on real-world tasks and problems. Gould & Weinberg (2014) stressed that psychological quality includes concentration, self-confidence, willpower, and so on. Research has shown that good psychological quality can improve individual performance and technical ability in competition.

The importance of socializing, and the development of connections are crucial to an individual's well-being and mental health. Human needs and social relation an opportunity to develop connections that can satisfy an individual's emotional needs and enhance self-esteem and a sense of belongingness. Holt-Lunstad, et al (2010) analyzed multiple studies and found a significant association between social connections and mortality risk. Lack of social connections increases an individual's risk of death, while positive social connections can extend life.

Table 4.3 shows significant differences in motivation levels among students learning table tennis through club mode teaching based major. The results indicate that both Age, and sex, being male and female data shows there are no significant differences in motivation levels regarding technology-related aspects, positive affective responses to the sport experience, inner drives to play for enjoyment, and deep passion and genuine love for table tennis. These findings suggest that teachers should consider the different motivations behind students' participation, particularly regarding majors to create more

inclusive and tailored teaching approaches that cater to the diverse needs and motivations of their students. Myers et al. (2020) showed that maintaining positive competitive relationships and respect helps to increase athletes' motivation to play, making them more competitive and confident in defeating their opponents.

The hypothesis for capabilities, opportunities, and motivation when grouped as to age was accepted. Capabilities in terms of sex and when grouped as to male and females was rejected. Moreover, opportunities and motivation in terms of sex and when grouped as to male and female was accepted. While capabilities, opportunities, and motivation in terms majors was rejected.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the researcher came up with the following conclusions.

The evaluation of students in table tennis reveals a high overall capability level in both physical and psychological dimensions through club mode teaching. This underscores the effectiveness of the integrated approach in cultivating well-rounded skills and highlights the success of the teaching methodology in enhancing student capabilities.

The evaluation of students in table tennis highlights a high overall opportunity level, considering both social and psychological dimensions through club mode teaching. This underscores the effectiveness of the integrated approach in providing diverse opportunities for community engagement, skill development, and overall well-being. The findings support the importance of a holistic approach in enhancing students' experiences and opportunities in the sport.

In conclusion, the evaluation of students in table tennis reveals a high overall motivation level through club mode teaching. The balanced integration of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation fosters a supportive environment where students engage in the sport for both enjoyment and external incentives. This comprehensive approach aligns with research emphasizing the importance of addressing diverse motivational factors for sustained engagement and performance in table tennis.

Therefore, in the capability level of the students in table tennis under the club mode teaching in terms of sex was rejected. The capability level, opportunity level, and motivation level of the students in table tennis under the club mode teaching when grouped in terms of Majors was rejected. The capability level, opportunity level, and motivation level of the students in table tennis under the club mode teaching when grouped in terms of age was accepted. The opportunity level and motivation level of the students in table tennis under the club mode teaching when grouped in terms of sex and when grouped as to male and female was accepted. Results provides an important indication for a thorough study on planning the club mode teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are given:

School Administrators. Encourage the adoption of club mode teaching in table tennis programs within the school. Allocate resources for facilities and provide support for teacher training in this methodology. Facilitate collaboration between teachers and external clubs to enrich the overall table tennis learning experience.

Coaches/Teachers. Embrace club mode teaching strategies in table tennis lessons, tailoring approaches to meet the diverse needs of students based on age, gender, and major. Actively engage students in the table tennis community, fostering inclusivity and a sense of belonging.

Table Tennis Students. Take an active role in leveraging the opportunities provided by club mode teaching. Participate enthusiastically in training, competitions, and community-building activities to enhance your skills and contribute to the vibrant table tennis community.

Future Researchers. Build on the current study as a foundation for future research on table tennis education. Explore additional factors influencing capability, opportunity, and motivation levels, contributing to the development of a robust evaluation framework. Consider longitudinal studies to track the long-term impact of club mode teaching.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare compliance in ethical standards. After getting the approval from the university administrators/heads, getting the permission from the teachers/trainers' and students to conduct the questionnaire. The researchers guaranteed that all the data gathered from the respondents remained confidential. Proper citations of related literature and studies are maintained. Moreover, there is no bias or prejudice in the findings and results of the study.

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